

Assessment of Causes and Implications of Violent Behaviours among Secondary School Students in Kwara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the causes and implications of violent behaviours among secondary school students in Kwara State. The research investigated if peer pressure and family problem are causes, and if poor academic performance and suicide thought are implications of violent behaviours among secondary school students in Kwara State. Descriptive research design of the survey type was adopted for the study and the population consists of all Secondary Schools students in Kwara state. Two hundred (200) respondents were selected through multistage sampling technique. A researcher structured questionnaire titled: Assessment of Causes and Implications of Violent behaviors Among Secondary School Students (AVBASS), validated and tested for reliability through test-retest method was used for data collection. A reliability coefficient of 0.72r was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient. Inferential statistics of Chi-Square was used to analyze the four hypotheses postulated at 0.05 alpha level. The result revealed that; peer pressure and family problem are causes (calc. χ^2 value of 162.39; 39.93 > tab. value of 16.92) respectively while poor academic performance and suicide thought are implications of violent behaviours (calc. χ^2 value of 41.30; 55.82 > the tab. χ^2 value of 16.92) at 9 df @ 0.05 alpha level. The researchers concluded that peer pressure, and family problem are causes of violent behaviour while poor academic performance and suicide thought are implications of violent behaviours among secondary school students in, Kwara State. The researchers recommend that students should be guided and encouraged to keep good company and maintain wholesome relationships among their peers.

Keyword: Students, violent behaviours, peer pressure, family problem, suicide

Introduction

School has always been an institution for learning and behavioural uprightness. It is looked up to by many stakeholders as an area for moral upbringing as well as avenue to correct moral decadence. Instead of living to this standard, school has been the major avenue for many moral decadences and violent behaviour lately. It houses bullying, indecent dressing, rape, cultism, alcoholism, among others. School, which ought to be the safest place for learners and teachers, has been the most dangerous place to be for them. It loses its aims, mission and vision. This could be a result of transfer of parent aggressiveness, peer influence and teachers' neglect or nonchalant attitudes. School violence in all its forms has led to students in particular, to many forms of physical disability, injury of various types, psychological distress, mental disorders, to list view.

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Violent behaviour among students is a major concern to the teachers, parents and all that are interested with the education of learners (Bardick & Bernes, 2018). The increasing school violence has become a problem that hinders the perception and reality of a school as a safe place for both pupils and teachers. Violence in schools may sometimes undermine the notion that school days are the happiest days in the learner's life. School violence wears many faces which include gang activities, locker theft, bullying, intimidation, discrimination, stigmatization, gun use and fighting (Basch, 2017). The focus of violence can be individuals, objects or the school itself. Both teachers and students may be affected by violence in schools. A learner can act violently towards other learners or can violently attack teachers.

Violence is a pervasive problem for Nigerians and at times, it is expressed in the most unlikely places under unexpected and unsettling conditions. It is usually expressed at home, school, in the neighborhood or in the community. In the secondary school system, the expression of aggressive behaviour is evident in the numerous and untold cruelties that some children inflict on their fellow learners. Over the years, a lot of blood lettings, massacre, maiming and killings have been observed in secondary schools (Carlson, 2020). At different-occasions students have been observed damaging school property, harassing their fellow students, threatening teachers who try stop them, especially in cases of examination supervision. These actions are confrontational and distractive, and could hinder adolescents from meeting up with the demands of their goals.

Violence could potentially make the learning environment threatening and uncondusive to learning, which, according to Denga (2018), could limit the learning performance of students. It could be argued that when students perceive threat arising from one form of aggression or the other, they may become destabilized as they would tend to spend the time meant for studying in finding ways to cope with the perceived threats. Clearly, any form of distraction within a learning setting is counter-productive. It is the researcher's belief that such distractions could constitute a hindrance to the State's ability to achieve her goal of self-reliance over the years. Nigeria as a nation understands and appreciates the fact that education is a precursor to nation building (National Policy on Education, 2013), and therefore considers education to be a catalyst for all aspects of development. In view of this, and in acknowledgment of the fact that the youth of today are the leaders of tomorrow, a great deal of resources has been directed toward providing education at both primary and secondary school level s. But rather than students of secondary schools devoting their times to learning, there is a tendency for many to spend their energy on the perpetuation of violence. This reduces the amount of time and level of concentration they put into their studies. It has been noted that students who experience stressful conditions are susceptible to go through unstable lives and poor academic performance (Addison-Wesley; Weaver, & Clum 2015).

Violent behaviour is a very complicated behaviour with a variety of multidimensional causes. In the past, social factors were mainly the center of attention for the researchers as causes of aggression in humans. But, with recent scientific and technological advancements, researchers are now trying to explore new areas, including biological factors. Nelson (2016) in his book has summarized the recent advancements in finding a relationship between biological factors and aggression. The major areas of interest include; molecular biology, genetics, nervous system, 5-HT, monoamines, neurotransmitters, nitric oxide (NO), the stimuli and situational factors, stress and drug abuse. Exposure to violent home and community environments, as well as injury due to violence, contribute to both reduced academic progress and increased disruptive or unfocused classroom behaviour for children, adolescents, and teenagers. It is estimated that between 10 and 20% of children in the United States are exposed to domestic violence annually and are physically injured (Carlson, 2020). Violence is positively associated with family size. Households who have more children are more likely to experience increased family conflict and child maltreatment which may lead to intrapersonal, interpersonal and academic limitations. Children affected by family and community violence suffer from lowered social and emotional competence and diminished academic performance (Burnham, 2019). With repeated exposure to traumatic events, a proportion of individuals may develop disorders characterized as Posttraumatic Stress and Oppositional Defiant. Given these issues, there is an increased need for school personnel to address the effects of violence on youth achievement in the classroom. Several researchers have shown the negative influence of school aggression on the classroom environment, and correspondingly how that negative environment affects students' behavioural adjustment at school and increases their involvement in misbehaviours and aggressive activities in the classroom (Carrasco & Trianes, 2015).

A classical experiment by Solomon Asch explains how a group of individuals can influence somebody in making a decision. Shuttle Worth (2017) noted that the Asch experiment was designed to test how peer pressure would influence the judgment and individuality of test subject to conform to the majority. It was found out that people frequently followed the majority judgement, even when the majority was wrong. People often accept to be influenced just for the desire to achieve a sense of security within a group that is of similar age culture, religion or educational status. Any unwillingness to be influenced carries with it the risk of social rejection and this is what young people fear most. Steinberg and Chung (2016) in their study found out that there was a link between peer group and aggressive behaviours. They established that children begin to depend

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on their peers for acceptance rather than their parents during adolescence. In addition, peer pressure becomes harder to resist at this stage such that the opinions of peers often matter more than those of parents. When adolescents formed relationships with people who displayed aggressive behaviours, they are likely to take part in the behaviours themselves. This was supported by Erickson, as cited by Kendra, (2022), that the resolution of adolescent developmental crisis depends on the interactions between the individual and whether support is provided by the environment. Therefore, if the significant person is practicing aggressive behaviours, the adolescent may engage in the same behaviour. Sense of belonging is a basic psychological need which will make students adapt to goals set by their peers. An adolescent would conform to peers because of the acceptance and the sense of belonging they got from the group. Affiliation to deviant peers represented the strongest predictor of deviant behaviour.

Bandura, as cited by Morales and Duenas, (2018), stated that adolescents are likely to do the same as their closest friends and will emulate the behaviour of their idol through observation and imitation. Peer group therefore provides a powerful opportunity for the formation of identity. According to Bandura peers may illicit or may serve as role models to other children who have a predisposition to act aggressively. He says that aggressive children are often friends of other oppositional, aggressive children. Current literature in education challenges school counsellors to expand their knowledge of social, environmental and family dynamics and the corresponding influences of those dynamics on violent student behaviour. This is because the roots of most violent behaviours appear to develop during childhood, the time when family members and family processes are characteristically the most prevalent influences in an individual's life (O'Moore 2018). Youth who commit the most serious violent acts, and who continue their violent acts beyond adolescence began their behaviours during childhood (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Substance Abuse Mental Health Services Administration [SAMHSA], 2017). The family is a central factor in the development and reduction of antisocial behaviours and delinquency. Consequently, school-based interventions to strengthen positive family involvement seem best suited to address the current trends in youth aggression and unmet mental health needs. To apply family-inclusive prevention and intervention approaches to student violence, school counsellors must first understand the antecedents of student violence that originate in the context and structure of the family.

A proportional relationship existed between academic performance and behaviour. Accomplishment issues can surface when students don't set objectives, don't arrange for how to achieve them, and don't sufficiently screen their advancement toward the objectives. Forceful conduct of a man has ability to disrupt the achievement of a set objective. For example, physical attack, tossing objects, property demolition and verbal dangers can hinder concentration on academic activities. Although the rate of suicidal behaviour among adolescents has increased dramatically over the last three decades, little is known about the prevalence and correlates of these behaviours in nonclinical samples of young people. Instead, current information relies heavily on data obtained from one of the following sources: clinical psychiatric populations; psychological autopsies; mortality statistics; attempted suicides reaching medical attention, and large-scale surveys, which have often failed to differentiate among specific categories of suicidal behaviours, thoughts, plans, attempts not requiring medical care, and attempts requiring medical care. Frequency estimates of all categories of suicidal behaviours in community samples of adolescents have varied from a low of 2% to a high of 63%(Carlson, 2020). Although a number of different correlates or predictors of suicidal thoughts, plans, and attempts have been addressed in many literatures, two factors-aggressive/impulsive behaviour and drug and alcohol use are rated very high among adolescents. Investigations focusing on the relationship between aggression and suicide have indicated that there is a very strong association between the two behaviours than has previously been identified. Shaffer, (2018) pointed out that there are two different clusters of suicidal individuals, the first characterized by aggressive and violent outbursts and the second characterized by depression or withdrawal. High incidences of suicidal behaviour have been described in samples of juveniles selected because of their history of violent or aggressive behaviours. Other researchers have reported that up to two thirds of suicide attempts among adolescents are impulsive in that they occur with little premeditation and are preceded only by a short period of planning (Cairns, Peterson & Neckerman, 2018). The widespread use of alcohol, other illicit drugs among adolescents is associated with violence and is identified as an influential factor contributing to observed increases in the rate of adolescent suicide.

Violence is a critical public health problem that has been increasing. Every year, more than one million people die because of violence and several nonfatal injuries occur as well. Moreover, violence adversely influences the quality of life apart from contributing to disease, death, and disability. Because violence affects the lives of millions in the long term, it is a risk factor for lifelong health and social problem. Adolescents as a whole are among the groups that are the most vulnerable to violence. In addition, violence caused by adolescents is one of the most overt forms of violence prevailing in the society. This period is a dynamic period wherein physical, psychological, and social maturity reach completion and adulthood-specific roles, responsibilities, and behaviours are acquired. Conversely, adolescents are both perpetrators and victims of violence, which does

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not only influence them but also affects their families, friends, and societies. Adolescents who are involved in an act of violence during high school usually continue this behaviour during their adulthood. Thus, there is a need to study the dimensions of violent adolescent behaviour to improve the health of adolescents and reduce problematic behaviours associated with violence. The aim of this study was to determine the causes and implications of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Ilorin metropolis, kwara State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

Generally, the study aims to investigate the causes and implications of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

1. to determine whether peer pressure is a cause of violent behaviour among secondary students in kwara state.
2. to assess whether family problem is a cause of violent behaviours among secondary school students in kwara state.
3. to examine if poor academic performance is an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara state
4. to investigate whether suicidal thought is an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara state

Research Questions:

The study sought to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the extent of peer pressure being a cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria?
2. What is the extent of family problem being a cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria?
3. What is the extent of poor academic performance being an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria?
4. What is the extent of suicide thought being an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were tested in the study;

1. Peer pressure will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria.
2. Family problem will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in . Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria?
3. Poor academic performance will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria.
4. Suicide thought will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Meropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Descriptive Survey research design was adopted for this study. The population for the study comprises all secondary school students in both private and public secondary schools in kwara state, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique consisting of purposive, proportionate and simple random sampling techniques was adopted for the study. Purposive sampling technique was used to select three senior secondary schools that have the highest population in each of the three political districts in the population. Proportionate technique was used to select 5% from the total number of classes available in each of the selected schools, while random sampling method was used to select 200 respondents across the selected schools and classes. A well-structured researchers' developed questionnaire titled Assessment of causes and implications of violent behavior among secondary school student (AVBASS) was used in collecting data for the study. The instrument was validated by experts in the related field and reliability of the instrument was ascertained through test re-test method. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to calculate the reliability of the instrument. A reliability coefficient of 0.72r was obtained and this was considered high enough for adoption for the study. Inferential statistics of Chi-Square was used to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

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Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent of peer pressure as a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara state?

Table 1: percentile analysis of peer pressure as a cause of violent behavior among students

ITEMS	SA	A	PR	D	SD	NR
1. At adolescent age, children are greatly influence by their peer behaviour which may be violence and aggressiveness	78 (39.0%)	80 (40.0%)	158	26 (13.0%)	16 (8.0%)	42
2. Students who associate with tout and delinquent friends are more likely to be violent in behaviour.	68 (34.0%)	88 (44.0%)	156	26 (13.0%)	18 (9.0%)	44
3. At adolescent age, children are characterized with action like bullying and they may be influence by their friends action in school	64 (32.0%)	62 (31.0%)	126	42 (21.0%)	32 (16.0%)	74
4. Friends in school and other places can force a students to engage in violent behaviour like cultism and vandalism.	62 (31.0%)	86 (43.0%)	148	28 (14.0%)	24 (12.0%)	52
Column Total Mean	272	316	147 (73.5%)	118	91	53 (26.5%)

Key: PR=Positive response, NR=Negative response

Table 1 shows that 147(73.5%) responded positively while 53(26.5%) responded negatively to the statements on the table, this implies that higher percentage agreed that peer pressure is a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara state, Nigeria.

Research Question 2

What is the extent of family problem as a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in kwara state?

Table 2: Percentile analysis of family problems as a cause of violent behavior

ITEMS	SA	A	PR	D	SD	NR
5. Children from a violent family are more likely to behave violently at school.	78 (39.0%)	80 (40.0%)	158	26 (13.0%)	16 (8.0%)	42
6. Lack of parental love, care and attention can lead to violent behaviour on students	68 (34.0%)	88 (44.0%)	156	26 (13.0%)	18 (9.0%)	44
7. Students whose family looks after are less susceptible to violent behaviour than students who are neglect.	62 (31.0%)	86 (43.0%)	148	28 (14.0%)	24 (12.0%)	52
8. Violent behaviour among adolescent can emanate from poor family background	64 (32.0%)	62 (31.0%)	126	42 (21.0%)	32 (16.0%)	74
Column Total Mean	272	316	147 (73.5%)	122	90	53 26.5%

Key: PR=Positive response, NR=Negative response

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Table 2 shows that 147(73.5%) responded positively while 53(26.5%) responded negatively to the statements on the table, this implies that higher percentage agreed that family problem is a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in kwara state, Nigeria.

Research Question 3

What is the extent of poor academic performance as an implication of violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara state?

Table 3: Percentile analysis of poor academic performance as an implication of violent behavior among secondary school students

ITEMS	SA	A	PR	D	SD	NR
9. Violent behaviour in school disrupt the school environment and affect school academic productivity.	80 (40.0%)	70 (35.0%)	150	34 (17.0%)	16 (8.0%)	50
10. Students who engage in violence behaviour doesn't have time for class and may affect their performance.	78 (39.0%)	78 (39.0%)	156	26 (13.0%)	18 (9.0%)	44
11. Teachers who teach in a school characterized by violent behaviour are going to teach under extreme fear which may affect their productivity.	82 (41.0%)	74 (37.0%)	156	30 (15.0%)	14 (7.0%)	44
12. Violence behaviour in school by students will generally affect the academic performance of every students	72 (36.0%)	90 (45.0%)	162	28 (14.0%)	10 (5.0%)	38
Column Total Mean	272	316	156 (78%)	118	58	44 (22%)

Key: PR=Positive response, NR= Negative response

Table 2 shows that 156(78%) responded positively while 44(22%) responded negatively to the statements on the table, this implies that higher percentage agreed that f is a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in kwara state, Nigeria.

Research Question 4

What is the extent of peer pressure as a cause of violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara state?

Table 4: Percentile analysis on suicidal thoughts as an implication of violent behavior among students

ITEMS	SA	A	PR	D	SD	NR
13. Victims of school violence like cultism are susceptible to suicide thought due to emotional and physical trauma	33 (15.0%)	106 (48.2%)	139	69 (26.8%)	22 (10.0%)	91
14. Violence behaviour like bully can make some students look down on themselves and try to kill themselves to avoid the bully.	16 (7.3%)	85 (45.9%)	101	101 (45.9%)	18 (8.2%)	119
15. Student who engage in violent may feel guilty of his or her action at one point and decide to commit suicide to avoid punishment.	55 (25.0%)	85 (45.9%)	140	61 (27.7%)	19 (8.6%)	80

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16. Violent behaviour in school and home is one of the leading causes of suicide and suicidal thoughts among adolescents.	55 (25.0%)	77 (35.0%)	132	75 (34.1%)	13 (5.9%)	88
Column Total Mean	159	353	128 (64%)	306	72	93 (36%)

Key: PR=Positive response, NR= Negative response

Table 4 shows that 128(64%) responded positively while 46(36%) responded negatively to the statements on the table, this implies that higher percentage agreed that suicidal thought is an implication of violent behavior among secondary school students in kwara state, Nigeria..

Hypothesis 1

Peer pressure will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Chi-square (χ^2) Results of Peer Pressure and Violent Behaviour among Students

S/N	ITEMS	df	Cal. Value	Table Value	Remarks
1	At adolescent age, children are greatly influence by their peer behaviour which may be violence and aggressiveness				
2	Students who associate with tout and delinquent friends are more likely to be violent in behaviour.				
3	At adolescent age, children are characterized with action like bullying and they may be influence by their friends action in school	9	162.39	16.92	Ho rejected
4	Friends in school and other places can force a students to engage in violent behaviour like cultism and vandalism.				
Column Total					

0.05 alpha level

Table 5: shows that the calculated chi-square value is 162.39 and the table value is 16.92 with the degree of freedom of 9 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the calculated χ^2 value is greater than the table value, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and the alternative hypothesis upheld. This implies that peer pressure is a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Hypothesis 2:

Family problem will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Table 6: Chi-square (χ^2) Results of Family Problem and Violent Behaviour among Students

S/N	ITEMS	df	Cal. Value	Table Value	Remarks
5.	Children from a violent family are more likely to behave violently at school.				
6.	Lack of parental love, care and attention can lead to violent behaviour on the part of a students.	9	31.93	16.92	Ho rejected
7.	Students whose family looks after are less susceptible to violent behaviour than students who are neglect.				
8.	Violent behaviour among adolescent can emanate from poor family background				
Column Total					

0.05 alpha level

Table 6: shows the calculated chi-square value is 31.93 and the table value χ^2 is 16.92 with the degree of freedom of 9 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the calculated chi-square value of 31.93 is greater than the table χ^2 value of 16.92 at 9 degree of

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freedom, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that family problem is a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Hypothesis 3:

Poor academic performance will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Table 7: Chi-square (χ^2) Results of Poor Academic Performance and Violent Behaviour among Students.

S/N	ITEMS	df	Cal. Value	Table Value	Remarks
15.	Violent behaviour in school disrupt the school environment and affect the overall school academic productivity.				
16.	Students who engage in violence behaviour doesn't have time for class and this may affect their academic performance.				
17.	Teachers who teach in a school characterized by violent behaviour are going to teach under extreme fear which may affect their productivity.	9	41.30	16.92	Ho rejected
18.	Violence behaviour in school by students will generally affect the academic performance of every students directly or indirectly involved.				
Column Total					

@0.05 alpha level

Table 7: shows that the calculated chi-square value of 41.30 and the table value of 16.92 with the degree of freedom of 9 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the calculated chi-square value is greater than the table value, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that poor academic performance is significantly an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Hypothesis 4: Suicide thought will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Table 8: Chi-square (χ^2) Results of Suicide Thought and Violent Behaviour among Students.

S/N	ITEMS	df	Cal. Value	Table Value	Remarks
19.	Victims of school violence like cultism are susceptible to suicide thought due to emotional and physical trauma				
20.	Violence behaviour like bully can make some students look down on themselves and try to kill themselves to avoid the bully.	9	55.82	16.92	Ho rejected
21.	Student who engage in violent may feel guilty of his or her action at one point and decide to commit suicide to avoid punishment.				
22.	Violent behaviour in school and home is one of the leading cause of suicide and suicidal thoughts among adolescents.				
Column Total					

@ 0.05 alpha level

Table 8: shows that the calculated chi-square value is 55.82 and the table value χ^2 is 16.92 with the degree of freedom of 9 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the calculated chi-square value of 55.82 is greater than the table χ^2 value of 16.92 at 9 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that suicide thought is significantly an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State.

Discussion of Findings

The result of research questions one and two reveal that higher percentage (73.5%) of respondents believed that peer pressure and family problem are some of the leading causes of violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara state. This is because secondary school students are mostly adolescents, and adolescence age is the age when young adults seek recognition and acceptance among their peers. Some adolescent even get depressed when they are isolated or got rejected by their class mates. Also, problems in the homes can push adolescents into the hands of violent friends who will teach them violent behaviours like bullying and fighting. Furthermore, higher percentage of the respondents agreed that violent behaviours can lead to poor academic performance and suicidal thoughts. This corroborate the fact about adolescents suffering from depression as a result of having to meet the demands by their violent peers. This is in line with the results of the postulated hypotheses which are reported below:

Hypothesis One which stated that peer pressure will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State was rejected and alternative hypothesis upheld. This means that peer pressure is a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State. This is because peer influence is associated with family role in promoting healthy or unhealthy behaviour during adolescence. Peer group is a model that influence behaviours and attitudes, towards accepting and adopting violence and fight due to excessive aggression. This finding corroborates the finding of Okorodudu (2015), who conducted a study to determine factors that are responsible for aggressive behaviours among secondary school students. His findings indicated that, as young people grow; they begin to surrender to the influence of their peers as they shed off their parental orientation and replace it with dependence on their peers. In the process, friends encourage their peers to engage in undesirable acts like fighting, alcohol consumption, sexual promiscuity and destruction of property. It is also observed that whenever incidence of violence are witnessed in school, a group of youths“ team up to engage in criminal activities. Peer groups do not only provide positive settings but peer pressure can also lead to risky behaviour and irresponsibility. Children who form friendships with anti- social peers are at the risk for later anti-social behaviour. When adolescents formed relationships with people who displayed aggressive behaviours, they often take part in the behaviours themselves. This was supported by Weerman,(2019),that the resolution of adolescent developmental crisis depends on the interactions between the individual and the environment. Therefore, if the significant person is practicing aggressive behaviours, the adolescent may engage in the same behaviour. If adolescents spend time with deviant peers who consumed drugs, fights, do not attend school regularly and are physically aggressive, the adolescents are more likely to engage in aggressive behaviours as well. They often do this to keep their friends and peers; to have a sense of belonging in a group or to boost their self-esteem.

Hypothesis Two which stated that family problem will not be a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State was rejected and alternative hypothesis upheld. This means that family problem is a significant cause of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State. This is because the family plays a major role in shaping the behaviour, attitude and morals of children. Family problems, such as physical abuse, battering and chaotic home environment have great influence on the temperament of children in adolescence and adulthood. Maladjustment, parent-child physical abuse, and Child-to-parent lack of emotional support, father and wrong parenting styles can be a precursor to violent behaviour among secondary school student. This result is in-line with the report of O’Moore, (2018) (who noted that the roots of most violent behaviours appear to develop during childhood, the time when family members live together and interact closely. Youth who commit most serious violent acts, and who continue their violent acts beyond adolescence began their behaviours during childhood (Weaver and Clum,2015).

Hypothesis three which stated that poor academic performance will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State was rejected. This is so because violence and fights due to excessive aggression could lead to absenteeism, lateness to school, distraction in classroom and poor academic achievement. This result is in-line with the report of Taylor; Davies & Malanchuk, (2017) who watched how and understudy self-regard, and levels of aggression influenced the academic performance in school. From the information, the authors identified a strong relationship between aggression and academic failure. Peaceful and friendly school and classroom environment foster better attention in the classroom and better attention and concentration improve learning and fosters better retention of knowledge. Hostile school environment, where bullies and haters display violent behaviour will affect better academic performance.

Hypothesis Four which stated that suicide thought will not significantly be an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in Kwara State was rejected. This means that suicide thought is significantly an implication of violent behaviour among secondary school students in kwara State. This implies that prolonged exposure to threat and other violent behaviours can lead to suicidal thought and attempts. This is supported by Shaffer (2018), who reported that there are two

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different clusters of suicidal individuals, the first characterized by aggressive and violent outbursts and the second characterized by depression or withdrawal. Investigations focusing on the relationship between aggression and suicide have indicated that there is a stronger association between the two behaviours than has previously been appreciated. Developmental research consistently documents the high levels of covariance between peer and youth deviance. It is becoming clear that one of the major ways that deviant youth become even more deviant is through unrestricted interaction with deviant peers. Adolescents sometimes join groups that readily accept them; even if the group is involved in illegal or negative activities. For them, the need for affiliation or closeness is often greater than the need to “do the right thing.” When adolescents are rejected, threatened or bullied, they often result to suicide to end it all rather than coping with rejection and isolation or constant threat from their classmates or school mates.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the significant role of peer pressure and family problems as causal factors contributing to violent behavior among secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria. Furthermore, it underscores the detrimental consequences of such behavior, including poor academic performance and the presence of suicidal thoughts among these students. These findings emphasize the urgent need for targeted interventions and support systems to address these issues and promote a safer and healthier educational environment for secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Students should be encouraged to keep good company, avoid the company of the violent people. Jingles, drama presentations and seminars should be organized periodically to correct any violent behaviour that might have been learnt at home.
2. Parents should be educated during school sport days and parents-Teachers’ association meetings to avoid violent behaviours at home and be very close to their wards.
3. Government should create and implement policy that will prevent hateful speech and violence in the school compound.
4. Schools should motivate counsellors to provide students with adequate knowledge on effect of violent behaviours so that they can also make informed decisions about their academics and health. Teachers should ensure that students are well coached on implication of violent behaviour on their psychological wellbeing.

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